

RESULTS OF ARCHAEOLOGICAL RESEARCH CONDUCTED AT SAMARKAND STATE UNIVERSITY**Tojiyev Sherzod**

PhD student at Samarkand State University

Annotasiya. Samarqand davlat universiteti arxeologlari O'zbekiston hududidagi ibtidoiy va qadimgi davr jamoalari madaniyatining kelib chiqishi tarixiy ildizlari va madaniy aloqalariga doir bir nechta tadqiqotlar olib bormoqda. Maqolada Samarqand davlat universiteti arxeologlarining so'nggi yillarda olib amalga oshirgan arxeologik tadqiqotlarning natijalari to'g'risida ma'lumotlar keltiriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Samarqand davlat universiteti, o'rta paleolit, so'nggi paleolit, paleometall davri, antik va o'rta asrlar arxeologiyasi, Samarqand paleolit makoni, Sug'd, Kofirqal'a.

Аннотация. Археологи Самаркандского государственного университета проводят ряд исследований исторических корней и культурных связей культуры первобытных и древних общин Узбекистана. В статье представлена информация о результатах археологических исследований, проведенных археологами Самаркандского государственного университета за последние годы.

Ключевые слова: Самаркандский государственный университет, средний палеолит, поздний палеолит, палеометаллический период, древняя и средневековая археология, Самаркандская палеолитическая стоянка, Согд, Кафиркала.

Abstract. Archaeologists of Samarkand State University are conducting several studies on the historical roots and cultural connections of the culture of primitive and ancient communities in Uzbekistan. The article provides information on the results of archaeological research carried out by archaeologists of Samarkand State University in recent years.

Key words: Samarkand State University, Middle Paleolithic, Late Paleolithic, Paleometallic period, ancient and medieval archeology, Samarkand Paleolithic site, Sughd, Kafirkala.

The Department of Archaeology of Samarkand State University was established in 1971. The scientists of the department carried out research that was important for the development of Central Asian archaeology. In 1947-1948, they discovered the Middle Paleolithic cave sites of Amonkoton and Takalisoy in the Urgut district and, based on the archaeological finds obtained during the excavations, scientifically substantiated the fact that the Zarafshan Valley was inhabited by humans since the Middle Paleolithic period (100-40 thousand years ago). In 1958-1969, D.N. Lev, together with M.D. Djurakulov, carried out excavations at the Samarkand site of the Upper Paleolithic (30-25 thousand BC) located in the territory of the city of Samarkand, and during the research, he obtained more than 10 thousand tools and other archaeological artifacts that scientifically shed light on the history of the life, economy and culture of primitive clans. Based on these archaeological sources, he substantiated that the site is a standard monument for the Upper Paleolithic period in Central Asia [2.B.129].

During 2009-2023, the members of the department identified the Karatov stone carving workshops and the Kokayoz specialized Paleolithic workshops, and a new classification of Central Asian Stone Age stone processing workshops was developed [6.B.193].

In recent years, members of the department have been conducting archaeological research not only in the Zarafshan oasis, but also in the Qoshrabot and Nurabad districts of the Samarkand region. Prof. N.A. Avanesova began researching monuments located near the Urganji village of the Qoshrabot district in 2013. According to preliminary results, it was

revealed that there are finds from the Bronze Age here [9.B.4]. In addition, since 2012, members of the department, as well as doctoral, master's and talented students, have been participating in the research of the international archaeological expedition at the Kafirkala monument in the Samarkand district.

Archaeological research was carried out on the basis of the project Cooperation in Science and Education (2018-2020) with Samarkand State University and the Eurasian Department of the German Institute of Archaeology. In particular, in March 2018, scientists of the department, in collaboration with Samarkand State University and the Eurasian Department of the German Institute of Archaeology, signed a scientific project agreement on "Organizing an Uzbek-German archaeological expedition and conducting reconnaissance work in the Zarafshan oasis" in 2018-2020. In this regard, an international expedition was organized and carried out in 2018-2020. During the research, about 30 burial mounds belonging to the "Andronova culture" of the Bronze Age (5-4 thousand years ago) were registered. One find site belonging to the Neolithic period was also identified. The stone artifacts recovered during the research can be divided into two periods. The Late Paleolithic flints, quartz flakes, and silicified limestone cores were dated to the Late Paleolithic due to their manufacturing technique and patina [7.B.317].

In 2022, research continued to be conducted on the archaeological study of the villages of Minishkar, Pangat, and Oboy in the Nurota mountain range and the creation of a map of the sites where Stone Age finds were found in the region. The ongoing research in the region will undoubtedly yield a number of scientific innovations in the study of the Stone Age archaeology of the Zarafshan valley.

Scientists from Samarkand State University are also conducting research on archaeological sites of ancient and medieval Sughd. As is known, Sughd is one of the major central cultural regions of Central Asia, and it is known from archaeological research that urban culture has been formed in this region since the early Iron Age [1.B.20]. The influence of the central city allowed the formation of rural and urban culture in areas favorable for agriculture.

As a result of joint research by the scientific staff of the Samarkand Institute of Archaeology and professors, teachers and students of Samarkand State University, new information was obtained about the early medieval urban and rural architecture of Central Sughd in the early medieval cities of Kafirkala and Kuldortepa, located in the southwestern part of Central Sughd, and in village mounds such as Rabodtepa II [5.B.100]. The architectural architecture of the early medieval monuments of Kafirkala, Kuldortepa and Rabodtepa II widely used the "balkhi dome" to cover the roofs of structures.

The scientific and pedagogical staff of the department are actively engaged in the study of our ancient cultural heritage, and in the upbringing and development of a talented generation of young personnel.

The main topics of the department's scientific research in recent years have been "Early civilizations in the territory of Uzbekistan: material and spiritual culture", "Historical roots of the origin and cultural ties of the culture of primitive and ancient communities in the territory of Uzbekistan", and scientific research has been carried out on them. During the years of its scientific and educational activity, the department has been publishing a collection of scientific articles entitled "Issues of archaeology, ancient history and ethnography", "Issues of archaeology of the Zarafshan valley". Also, the professors, teachers, and researchers of the department have published about 20 monographs (also published in foreign languages) and about 1,000 scientific articles over the past years.

Samarkand State University research allows us to shed new light on the material culture of the Zarafshan oasis:

1. The Zarafshan valley, due to its natural and geographical location, is the central part of not only Uzbekistan, but also the Central Asian region. This land has been inhabited by humans since the Muste period of the Old Stone Age. Since this period, archaeological monuments have been found relating to all stages of human history, and based on these sources of material culture, the history of the primitive period of the oasis population has been studied in a gradual sequence [8.B.416].

2. The research has shown that the ancient culture of the Zarafshan oasis, with its diversity, each period and its stages of intensive development in the historical sequence, has left a great cultural heritage in the history of mankind.

3. The research has yielded valuable information on the paleogeographic, paleogeological, hydromorphological, and modern physical and geographical areas of the oasis.

4. The fact that the Middle Zarafshan oasis is a kind of "micro-cultural oasis" in the study of the material culture of the Stone Age communities of the northern slopes of the Koratapa mountain massif was scientifically substantiated, the issue of the continuity of the culture of the communities, their autochthony was resolved: the monument of the Olmabulok Mustye period, the lower cultural layer of the Ochilgor site (11th-9th millennia BC; Karakamar, Sazag'on 1 - the last stage of the Mesolithic period (8th-7th millennia BC), the upper cultural layer of the Ochilgor site, Sazag'on 2 - Neolithic (7th-5th millennia BC), Tapaqu 4 - Neolithic (6th-4th millennia BC), Jangal 1, Tapaqu 3 - Neolithic (5th-3rd millennia BC).

5. The boundaries of the distribution of monuments related to the culture of the Sazag'on Neolithic communities were determined: mainly the monuments of the Middle Zarafshan oasis. The Koratapa mountain range is located in a micro-oasis on the northern slope, and to the southeast are the monuments of the Hissar Neolithic culture of the Central Asian mountain region of Tajikistan (Oqtanga, Kangurtut), to the south is the waist of the Koratapa mountain range (Tashkoton, Kyzyltash, Amir Temur Cave) and on the southern slope are the side gorges of the Katta Kuruksay, Kyzylolmasay and finds of stone tools from the Taragay village, to the northwest is the Lower Zarafshan lowland region (finds of Jom, Tim, monuments of Uchtut, Ijont, Chorbakti, Dorbazakir 1, 2).

6. In the system of monuments of the Sazagon culture, in the example of the Ochilgor site, a whole complex of sources expressing the content related to fire, religious beliefs related to totemism, drawings, rituals from the cultural layer (remains of the hearth in a circular form, remains of animal bones in a circular form) mounds, circular stone devices, and between these devices, the complete body bones of a goat) were found, and it was first introduced into the science of Central Asian Stone Age archaeology and recognized by experts as a religious belief complex.

7. The Zarafshan Valley was extensively developed during the Bronze Age. Now not only its hilly regions, but also the steppe and desert regions and future oases were developed. By this time, significant socio-economic and ethnocultural changes were taking place in the life of our primitive ancestors. The first division of labor occurs in the economic life of society, that is, animal husbandry is separated from primitive agriculture, and these two branches, two directions of the economy begin to develop independently, based on the natural and geographical conditions of the places and their ecological potential.

8. The first urban processes in the Zarafshan Valley, according to the analysis of archaeological materials, began in the period of Sarazm, when the ancient agricultural culture was formed (Sarazm II). The monumental buildings of a social and religious nature found in Sarazm, the metallurgical crafts associated with the mining industry, the rise of various labor

and military weapons from stone to the level of art; the high level of production of fire-worshipping temples and related religious ritual objects; the interregional trade of metal raw materials produced by Sarazm metallurgists; the formation of the steppe trade caravan route through Jam, etc., testified to the urban processes that took place and are developing rapidly in the valley.

9. The Zarafshan Valley occupies an important place in the history of Central Asian culture due to the abundance of monuments, their diversity and belonging to different periods. Its territory has been mastered since the Muste stage of the Old Stone Age. The diversity of ancient cultures, each period and the stages of their intensive development in historical succession have left a great cultural heritage in the history of mankind.

REFERENCES.

1. Бердимуродов А.Э., Богомолов Г.И., Асланов А.П., Археологическое изучение городища Кафиркала: отчет за 2016 год // Архив Института археологии АН РУз. С. 20, 25.
2. Djurakulova D.M. Tangible Cultural Heritage of the Silk Road from the Area of Modern Uzbekistan. The Role of Archaeologists at Samarkand State University in the Study of Archaeological Sites on the Great Silk Road. Lublin, 22 mart, 2021. -P. 129-133.
3. Djuraqulova D.M. Samarqand makoning madaniy-davriy xususiyatlariga doir muloxazalar SamDU Axborotnomasi, №2 (108). Samarqand, 2018. -B. 13-17.
4. Воронина В.Л. Архитектура древнего Пянджикента. Труды ТАЭ. Т.III, МИА, №66. 1958.С.212.
5. Сандибоев А.Н. 2023 yilda Quldortepa yodgorligida olib borilgan arxeologik tadqiqotlar. Ўзбекистонда археологик тадқиқотлар. №16. 2024, 100-103 б
6. Эргашев О.Т Место памятников Кукаяз 1-8 в классификации центральноазиатских мастерских каменного века. Археология Евразийских степей №1, 2023. С.190-194.
7. Эргашев О.Т., Раджабов А., Ёркулов А., Бердикулов М., Имомов А., Унгалов Л., Бахронов А. Самарқанд вилояти худудидаги тош даврига оид ёдгорликларда олиб борилган археологик қидирув тадқиқотлари бўйича ҳисобот. Сайфуллаев Б., Ўзбекистонда археологик тадқиқотлар:2022. №15. Б. 317-322.
8. Холматов.Н.У. 2023 йилда Сазоғон 3 ёдгорлигида олиб борилган археологик қазув тадқиқоти. Ўзбекистонда археологик тадқиқотлар. №16. 2024, 416-421 б.
9. E.Luneau., N. Avanesova., O.Ergashev., G.Giraud., R.Housse ., A.Kholmatov., L.M. Rouse., F. Schreiber. Inhabiting the central Asian mountains: Study of modern campsites from the Nuratau range, Uzbekistan. Quaternary International . V.700. B.4